

Complexes of 3-(4-Pyridyl)Triazoline-5-Thione with Mn(II), Ti(III), Fe(III) and Zr(IV)

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Complexes of 3-(4-pyridyl)triazoline-5-thione with Mn(II), Fe(III), Ti(III) and Zr(IV) have been synthesised and characterised on the basis of physicochemical investigations including infrared and electronic spectroscopy and magnetic moment measurements. They have been assigned the formula $[\text{Mn}(3,4\text{PT}5\text{TH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2$, $[\text{Fe}(3,4\text{PT}5\text{T})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}$, $[\text{Ti}(3,4\text{PT}5\text{T})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}$ and $[\text{Zr}(3,4\text{PT}5\text{T})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, respectively. Chlorine atoms are found to be in ionic state. Magnetic moment data and electronic spectra indicate that the Mn(II) complex is tetrahedral but Ti(III), Fe(III) and Zr(IV) complexes are octahedral in which two water molecules are at *trans* positions. Metal-ligand vibrations have also been assigned.

IN continuation of our work¹⁻³ on the complexes of 3-(4-pyridyl)triazoline-5-thione (I), we report here the synthesis and characterisation of Mn(II), Ti(III), Fe(III) and Zr(IV) complexes of I.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. or C.P. quality. The ligands, 3-(4-pyridyl)triazoline-5-thione was prepared by the method of Dutta *et al*⁴.

3-(4-Pyridyl)triazoline-5-thionetriaquo manganese(II) chloride $[\text{Mn}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(3,4\text{PT}5\text{TH})]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{MnCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (~ 0.3 g) was dissolved in distilled water and the solution was filtered. The ligand (~ 0.8 g) in boiling alcohol was mixed with the $\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution so that M:L ratio was 1 : 3, and the mixture was refluxed for 5 hr. Excess of pyridine was added into it when all the ligand dissolved and the solution was filtered. The filtrate was evaporated to a small volume. After refluxing again for another 2 hr, the solution was evaporated almost to dryness. The resulting light yellow complex was washed with cold ethanol and ethyl methyl ketone and dried at 120° in an electric oven. (Found : C, 25.96 ; H, 2.54 ; N, 13.9 ; Cl, 20.0. Calcd. ; C, 23.50 ; H, 3.30 ; N, 15.6 ; Cl, 19.8%).

Diaquodi { 3-(4-pyridyl)triazoline-5-thione } titanium(III) chloride $[\text{Ti}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(3,4\text{PT}5\text{T})_2]\text{Cl}$: This complex was prepared by mixing hot ethanolic solution of the ligand (~1.0 g) with titanous chloride (~0.31 g) solution in dilute HCl (2 N) such that the molar ratio of the metal ion to the ligand was 1 : 3. Deep yellow coloured complex precipitated out which was filtered, washed thoroughly with ice cold ethanol

and ether and dried in an electric oven at 110° for 2 hr. (Found : C, 36.84 ; H, 3.40 ; N, 24.01 ; Cl, 7.2. Calcd. ; C, 35.44 ; H, 2.95 ; N, 23.60 ; Cl, 7.5%).

Diaquodi { 3-(4-pyridyl)triazoline-5-thione } iron(III) chloride $[\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(3,4\text{PT}5\text{T})_2]\text{Cl}$: The ligand (~ 1.0 g) was dissolved in boiling alcohol (~ 100 ml). Ferric acetate (~ 0.5 g) was dissolved in minimum volume of dil.HCl (2 N) and filtered. The ferric acetate solution was mixed with the ligand solution and the mixture was refluxed for 4 hr and filtered. The yellow coloured filtrate was evaporated almost to dryness resulting in the formation of yellowish brown crystals of the complex. The complex was washed with ethanol and ether and dried in an electric oven at 120° for 2 hr. (Found : C, 35.05 ; H, 2.91 ; N, 23.10 ; Cl, 6.87. Calcd. ; C, 34.90 ; H, 2.90 ; N, 23.23 ; Cl, 7.36%).

Diaquodi { 3-(4-pyridyl)triazoline-5-thione } zirconium(IV) chloride tetrahydrate $[\text{Zr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(3,4\text{PT}5\text{T})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Zirconium nitrate (~ 0.51 g) was dissolved in distilled water and the solution filtered into a hot ethanolic solution of the ligand (~ 0.8 g). The mixture was refluxed for 3 hr, cooled and dil. HCl added into it when all the ligand dissolved. The solution was filtered and the filtrate evaporated almost to dryness when yellow crystals of the complex was obtained which was washed with ethanol and ether and dried at 120° in an electric oven. (Found : C, 26.53 ; H, 3.18 ; N, 18.0 ; Cl, 11.6. Calcd. ; C, 26.90 ; H, 3.50 ; N, 18.0 ; Cl, 11.3%).

Results and Discussion

Analytical data of the complexes indicate the following stoichiometry :

- (i) $\text{Mn}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(3,4\text{PT}5\text{TH})\text{Cl}_2$,
- (ii) $\text{Ti}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(3,4\text{PT}5\text{T})_2\text{Cl}$,
- (iii) $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(3,4\text{PT}5\text{T})_2\text{Cl}$,
- (iv) $\text{Zr}(3,4\text{PT}5\text{T})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

These complexes were found to be soluble in DMF indicating that they are most probably monomeric. The Mn(II) complex is light yellow in colour while the Fe(III) complex is brownish yellow, the Ti(III) complex is golden yellow and the Zr(IV) complex is yellow. Estimation of chlorine indicates that Cl atoms are in ionic form in these complexes. Conductivity of the complexes has been measured in DMF solution and found to exhibit molar conductivity equal to 150, 140, 85 and 90 mhos for Mn(II), Zr(IV), Fe(III) and Ti(III) complexes, respectively indicating that Mn(II) and Zr(IV) complexes have three ions each while Fe(III) and Ti(III) complexes have two ions each. They may, thus, be formulated as $[\text{Mn}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3(3,4\text{PT5TH})]\text{Cl}_2$, $[\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(3,4\text{PT5T})_2]\text{Cl}$, $[\text{Ti}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(3,4\text{PT5T})_2]\text{Cl}$. In case of Zr(IV) complex, 4 molecules water is expelled at 120° and hence it may be formulated as $[\text{Zr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(3,4\text{PT5T})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Magnetic measurements by means of Gouy balance indicate that the complex $[\text{Mn}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(3,4\text{PT5TH})]\text{Cl}_2$ has a magnetic moment equal to 5.8 B.M. Thus, five unpaired electrons are present in the complex molecule. Obviously, the hybridisation of Mn(II) ion in the complex is either sp^3 or sp^3d^2 . However, sp^3 hybridisation and tetrahedral structure of this complex is preferred over octahedral structures because all bands in the visible region are above 20000 cm^{-1} . It has been observed by several workers⁵⁻⁸ that tetrahedral Mn(II) complexes exhibit absorption bands above 20000 cm^{-1} and octahedral Mn complexes exhibit at least one band below 20000 cm^{-1} . The absence of Mn(III) ion is indicated by the absence of a band at about 16000 cm^{-1} in the visible spectrum of the present complex. This is also obvious from the presence of three water molecules and one ligand molecule and also from the ionic nature of the Cl^- ions. In most of the octahedral complexes⁹, there is a strong band in the region of 25000-27000 cm^{-1} but there is no band in this region in this complex. Thus, tetrahedral structure may be tentatively suggested for the complex, $[\text{Mn}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(3,4\text{PT5TH})]\text{Cl}_2$. Very strong intensity of the bands¹⁰ observed at 29200 cm^{-1} and 28100 cm^{-1} in the present case also supports the tetrahedral structure of this complex.

The complex $[\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(3,4\text{PT5T})_2]\text{Cl}$ has a magnetic moment of 6.1 B.M. Thus, it may be a spin-free octahedral complex. The electronic spectrum of the complex has very weak bands at 1425 $m\mu$, 870 $m\mu$. These bands indicate the octahedral structure and oxidation number of +3 of the iron in the complex. Band below 500 $m\mu$ have become submerged in strong charge transfer bands.

The titanium(III) ion is a d^2 -system. The present complex $[\text{Ti}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(3,4\text{PT5T})_2]\text{Cl}$ has an effective magnetic moment of 1.8 B. M. corresponding to one unpaired electron. The electronic spectrum of this complex has a band below 450 $m\mu$ corresponding to $t_{2g} \rightarrow e_g$ transition. Thus, octahedral structure may be assigned to this complex.

The Zr(IV) complex $[\text{Zr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(3,4\text{PT5T})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is a diamagnetic complex. It is a d^0 -system.

Its 4d, 5s and 5p orbitals are vacant. Hence, it can undergo special types of hybridization using the vacant orbitals. Its two chlorine atoms are ionizable. It has thus, most probably, formed octahedral complex. Coordination number equal to six is common for Zr(IV) ion^{11, 12}.

Infrared spectra : The infrared bands of interest of the ligand and the complexes are discussed in the text below. A comparison of the infrared spectra of the ligand and complexes indicates the following :

- (i) Two bands having contributions from νNH and νCH are present at 3120 and 3080 cm^{-1} in the infrared spectrum of Mn(II) complex. But there is only one band centred at 3080 cm^{-1} in the infrared spectra of Fe(III), Ti(III) and Zr(IV) complexes. This suggests that H-atom of one of the two N-H groups of the ligand has been replaced by the metal ion in these complexes.
- (ii) The thioamide band IV assigned to $\nu\text{C}=\text{S}$ mode is observed at 850 cm^{-1} in the ir spectrum of the ligand but this shifts to 820 cm^{-1} in the complexes, indicating coordination of the ligand to the metal ions through sulphur¹³⁻²⁰. An extra strong band is present in the 800-805 cm^{-1} region in the complexes of Fe(III), Ti(III) and Zr(IV) complexes, probably because of their octahedral structure but no such band is present in the Mn(II) complex as it is not an octahedral complex.
- (iii) The absence of one of the two νNH bands in Fe(III), Ti(III) and Zr(IV) complexes and presence of metal-sulphur bonds indicate that coordination to central metal ions has occurred through both nitrogen and sulphur atoms of the ligand.
- (iv) All the complexes contain weak to medium intensity broad bands centred at 3400, 1630 and 740 cm^{-1} . They may be due to $\nu\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\delta\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\pi\text{H}_2\text{O}$ modes of coordinated water in the complexes²¹⁻²³.
- (v) There is a weak and broad shoulder at 455 cm^{-1} and a medium band at 540 cm^{-1} in the ir spectrum of Zr(IV) complex. These may be assigned to $\nu\text{Zr}-\text{O}^{\text{so}}$ and $\nu\text{Zr}-\text{N}^{\text{sl}}$ modes of vibration.
- (vi) There is a medium band at 510 cm^{-1} in the ir spectrum of the Ti(III) complex which may be assigned to $\nu\text{Ti}-\text{O}$ + ligand vibrational modes. Probably, $\nu\text{Ti}-\text{N}$ falls below 400 cm^{-1} .
- (vii) The $\nu\text{Fe}-\text{O}$ and $\nu\text{Fe}-\text{N}$ modes are observed at 540 and 470 cm^{-1} , respectively in the ir spectrum of the Fe(III) complex.
- (viii) Broad weak bands at 470 and 430 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the Mn(II) complex may be assigned to $\nu\text{Mn}-\text{O}$ modes of vibration. $\nu\text{Mn}-\text{S}$ band probably lies below 400 cm^{-1} . The presence of two $\nu\text{Mn}-\text{O}$ modes indicates the presence of two types of coordinated water.
- (ix) The presence of only one ν metal-oxygen band in Fe(III), Ti(III) and Zr(IV) complexes indicates that their coordinated water molecules

are at *trans* positions. More than one ν Mn—O bands are in agreement with the tetrahedral structure of the Mn(II) complex.

Thus, on the basis of aforesaid arguments the following tentative structures may be assigned to these four complexes

Tetrahedral structure of Mn(II) complex cation.

Octahedral structure of Fe(III), Ti(III) and Zr(IV) complexes. M = Fe(III), Ti(III) or Zr(IV); n = 1 for Fe(III) and Ti(III) complexes and 2 for Zr(IV) complex. x = 0 for Fe(III) and Ti(III) complexes, and 4 for Zr(IV) complex.

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